

Kinetics of Oxidation of Toluenes by Transition Metals V^v ^{1,2}.

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The kinetics of the oxidation of toluenes and nitro toluenes by V^v is discussed. The kinetic process is total second order in both the oxidant and substrate. The reaction constant ρ is computed and it has value -3.75. The molecular radius of the activated complex has been calculated. Bunnett treatment has been applied and parameter ω is computed. Mn^{++} has been found to accelerate the process. The reaction has been found to have dependence on H_0 . Variation of dielectric constant has notable effect on the process. A mechanism to explain all the salient features is postulated.

Ogata *et al*³, studied the kinetics of oxidation of toluenes by Chromic Acid in Acetic acid medium, and assumed a rate law $V = k[\phi - CH_3][Cr_2O_7]^{2/3}[H^+]^n$ where the order with respect to the concentration of the acid was not clearly defined. They proposed a mechanism involving two moles of chromic acid on the hydrocarbon in the rate determining step to form a species having two Chromium-Carbon bonds; with a subsequent rearrangement to a structure similar to Etard complex. They observed that electron withdrawing groups retard the reaction. But the mechanism postulated by them is not clear as they do not clarify how the Etard complex rearranges to yield a carboxylic acid. Ananta Krishnan, Radhakrishna Murti and Varadarajan⁴ studied the oxidation of toluenes by Chromic acid and found third order with respect to Chromic acid which could be either taken to mean that all the three hydrogen atoms are lost in the rate determining step or the hydrogens are lost stepwise in three individual rate processes. Thus it is clear that these oxidations are not clearly understood and hence this investigation was undertaken to throw further light on the mechanism of oxidation of the aromatic hydrocarbons with a different oxidant of transition group, i.e. V^v .

EXPERIMENTAL

Acetic acid has been purified by the usual procedure. Toluene (boiling point 110° and refractive index 1.4969) was purified by distillation, *m*-nitrotoluene (boiling point 230° and refractive index 1.547) was purified by distillation and *p*-nitrotoluene (melting point 54°) was purified by recrystallization.

1. A preliminary communication on this has been published in *Chem. & Ind. (London)* 1966, **41**, 1722.
2. Accepted and presented at 54th session, Indian Science Congress Association held at Hyderabad 1967. Abstracts Part III, Section IV, Page 95.
3. Y. Ogata, A. Fukui and S. Yuguchi, *J. A. C. S.* 1952, **74**, 2707.
4. S. V. Ananta Krishnan, P. S. Radhakrishna Murti and R. V. Varadarajan. Abstracts Sri Venkateswar University Seminar, October 1965.

V^v solutions were prepared by dissolving V₂O₅ in sulphuric acid of required acidity. The solutions were perfectly homogenous.

Procedure adopted for estimation was to quench the reaction mixture in excess of Ferrous Ammonium Sulphate and back titrating the Ferrous Ammonium Sulphate with standard dichromate solution.

In all cases the products have been identified as their respective 2-4 Dinitro-phenyl-hydrazones.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results are interesting, that unlike the chromic acid oxidation of toluenes, where a second order or third order is postulated with respect to the oxidant alone, these oxidations are strikingly different that they follow a total second order kinetics with respect to the oxidant and substrate in acidic media (8N). The oxidation does not occur at lower acidities irrespective of the temperature. The reaction follows the rate expression

$$V = k[\phi - \text{CH}_3][\text{V}^{\text{v}}][\text{h}_0]$$

This is the first report of such a rate process being observed in case of toluenes. A similar observation has been made by Wiberg⁵ in his studies of oxidations of diphenyl methanes with chromic acid. The rate determining step may be the abstraction of hydride ion

which now undergoes fast decomposition to yield the aldehyde, which is the final product identified as the respective 2 : 4 dinitro-phenyl hydrazone.

Effect of acidity on reaction kinetics.

TABLE 1

Compound- <i>m</i> -Nitro toluene	Temperature 60° Percentage of Acetic acid (v/v) 70%
Acidity	$k \text{ moles}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$
8.1 N	7.720×10^{-4}
9.45 N	1.195×10^{-8}
10.8 N	2.260×10^{-8}

This oxidation is an acid catalysed process and is more probably related to H₀ function than to H⁺ ion concentration (Zucker-Hammett hypothesis)⁶. The active species is pervanadyl ion VO₂⁺ which is a powerful oxidant.

5. K. B. Wiberg and R. J. Evans, *Tetrahedron*, 1960, 8, 313.
6. L. Zucker and L. P. Hammett, *J. A. C. S.*, 1939, 61, 2791.

When a plot is drawn with $\log k$ vs H_0 linearity is observed and the slope is found to be 1.09 which comparable to the results reported by Wiberg (loc. cit.) and Rocek and Krupicka⁷ for alcohols where the slopes were 1.00 and 0.92 respectively. This shows first order dependence on acidity.

Bunnett⁸ treatment has been applied, wherein the number and role of water molecules in the transition state may be estimated by evaluating the parameter ω the slope of the plot of $\log k + H_0$ against $\log aH_2C$. The ω value obtained is 0.3162.

Effect of change of composition of the solvent : The change in solvent composition of acetic acid leads to acceleration as observed in the oxidations of alcohols⁹. The reaction rate increasing with decrease in dielectric constant, shows the nature of the process as positive ion and dipole reaction.

TABLE 2

Acidity-8.1 N (Sulphuric Acid) Temperature 60° Percentage of Acetic Acid	Compound Toluene. k moles ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	Acidity-10.8 N (Sulphuric Acid) Temperature 80° Percentage of Acetic Acid	Compound- <i>m</i> - Nitro toluene k moles ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
50	3.343 × 10 ⁻³	50	7.681 × 10 ⁻³
60	8.671 × 10 ⁻³	60	1.370 × 10 ⁻³
70	34.46 × 10 ⁻³	70	2.822 × 10 ⁻³

For the limiting case of 'head on' approach of an ion to a dipolar molecule, the equation given below was developed by Amis.¹⁰

$$\ln k'_{D=D} = \ln k'_D = \alpha + \frac{ze\mu}{DkTr^2}$$

According to this equation, if dielectric constant is increased, the rate should increase for a negative ionic reactant and vice versa for a positive ionic reactant.

A plot of $\log k$ vs $1/D$ showed linearity with a slope of 1.2 and computation of molecular radius yielded a value of 6.4 A.U. which is quite reasonable for ion-dipole reactions.

Effect of change of structure :—Bond fission becomes exceptionally difficult because of nitro deactivation. Para nitro is much more retarded than meta as there is the buttressing effect of resonance.

TABLE 3

Acidity-8.1 N Compound	70% Acetic Acid	Temperature 60° k moles ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
Toluene		0.3446
Meta nitro toluene		0.000772
Para nitro toluene		0.000531

7. J. Roolk and J. Krupicka, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1958, 23, 2068.
8. J. F. Bunnett, *J.A.C.S.*, 1961, 83, 4956.
9. W.A. Waters, *Mechanism of oxidation of organic compounds*; 1964.
10. E. S. Amis, *J. Chem. Edn.*, 1953, 30, 351.

A plot of $\log k$ vs σ showed linearity as well as with a plot of $\log k$ vs σ^+

TABLE 4

Compound	$\log k$	σ	σ^+
<i>p</i> -nitro toluene	4.7251	0.778	0.777
<i>m</i> -nitro toluene	4.8875	0.710	0.662
Toluene	1.5374	0.000	0.000

TABLE 5

Percentage of Acetic acid 60%	Temperature 80°
Concentration of Mn ⁺⁺ 0.002342 M	Acidity—10.8 N
<i>m</i> -Nitro toluene without Mn ⁺⁺	1.370×10^{-3} moles ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
<i>m</i> -Nitro toluene with Mn ⁺⁺	3.554×10^{-3} moles ⁻¹ min ⁻¹

The reaction constant ρ has a value of -3.75 . The ω value obtained as per the Bunnett treatment by plotting $\log k + H_0$ against $\log a_{H_2O}$ has a value 0.3162. With Mn⁺⁺ a threefold acceleration has been observed. All these point to an S_N² mechanism leaning considerably to S_N'. The transition state may be pictured as follows

The most important bond breaking process in the above mechanism involves loss of hydrogen as a hydride anion. The reaction could be expected to have a large negative ω value if it is a simple carbonium ion process. A reaction which involves the nucleophilic participation of a molecule of water has been shown to have a large ω value ranging from $+1.2$ to $+3.3$. The low ω value of 0.3162 could be rationalised on the basis of above mechanism. The large negative ω value, characteristic of the developing carbonium ion character is counterbalanced by the nucleophilic push by a molecule of water (with ω positive) with a resultant low ω value. Low ω values have been reported by Bunton and coworkers¹³ in their glycoside hydrolysis and exchange reactions.

The low ω value and the high ρ value observed in these oxidations lead us to believe that the above mechanism is probably operating in the reaction. Solvent influences also support the above mechanism as with decrease in Dielectric constant the reaction rate increases consistent with the dispersal of charges in the transition

11. L. P. Hammett. 'Physical Organic Chemistry', 1940, p. 188.
12. H. C. Brown, and Y. Okamoto, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, 22, 485.
13. C. A. Bunton, and D. R. Llewellyn, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 3402.

state¹⁴. It is proper to recall that SN_2 reactions have ρ values of -3 to -4 ¹⁵. The acceleration observed with Mn^{++} should be commented upon. If the premise that the initial reaction involves a two electron transfer is accepted one could explain the accelerating influence due to Mn^{++} . V^v and V^{IV} have no action on Mn^{++} and if it were a simple one electron transfer process there should not have been any threefold acceleration as observed. Cumulatively the acceleration observed with Mn^{++} the high ρ value and low ω value all could be rationalized on the mechanism postulated above. The probable intermediate valence states, when Mn^{++} is initially added to the reaction may be pictured as follows :—

The Mn^{+++} is probably converted to MnO_2 . V^v does not react with Mn^{++} in this system. This has been checked by an independent experiment. This is postulated on analogy with Cr^{IV} and Mn^{II} reaction in chromic acid oxidation. The result is in contrast to the effect of Mn^{++} (0.002342 M concentration) in chromic acid oxidations in general where retardation has been observed except in a few cases like oxidation of lactic acid and *pp'* dimethoxy diphenyl methane.

Effect of temperature :—The computation of activation energy yielded a value of 19.68 k cal, which is quite reasonable for second order reactions. A plot of $\log k$ vs $1/T$ showed perfect linearity.

TABLE 6

Compound-Toluene	Acidity—8.1 N
	50% Acetic Acid
Temperature	k moles ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
60°	0.03343
70°	0.05779
80°	0.1717

Nature of species :—In sulphuric acid solutions the species seems to be according to Waters ($V:O(OH_2)SO_4^+$) and in Perchloric acid medium the species is per vanadyl ion Vo_2^+ . There is no controversy regarding the cationic nature of the species which is in consonance with the effect of dielectric constant. Further work is necessary to confirm the nature of the species.

Experiments conducted on methoxy toluenes show that they require low acidities and low temperature to follow the kinetics. In these cases also the reaction

14. Ingold, C.K., 'Structure and Mechanism of Organic Chemistry', 1953.

15. K.B. Wiberg, 'Physical Organic Chemistry', 1964, p. 414.

follows second order, and the work on methoxy toluenes confirms that in all the cases it is a two electron transfer.

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